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Abstract`

Nursing students face elevated risks of anxiety and depression due to academic demands and professional training environments. This study explored the impact of anxiety and depression on everyday memory. A sample of 288 female diploma nursing students (aged 18–24, mean age 19.8 years) was purposively selected from two public nursing institutes in the Dhaka division of Bangladesh. Data collection utilized Bangla-translated versions of the Beck Anxiety Inventory, Beck Depression Inventory-II, and the Cognitive Failure Questionnaire. Correlation analysis demonstrated a significant positive association among anxiety, depression, and cognitive failures. Multiple regression analysis further revealed that anxiety and depression each made a significant, independent contribution to the variance in everyday memory, jointly accounting for 32.7% of the total variance. These findings highlight crucial implications for healthcare professionals, educators, and policymakers regarding student mental health and clinical safety.

Anxiety, Depression, and Everyday Memory among Female Students pursuing Diploma in Nursing

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Nursing students are susceptible to higher risks of anxiety and depression. We tested the prediction that anxiety and depression might adversely affect everyday memory on 288 female students pursuing diploma in nursing who have been selected purposively from two public nursing institutes of Dhaka division of Bangladesh. The students were between the ages of 18 to 24 years, with a mean age being 19.8 years. Data were collected using a questionnaire package comprised of Bangla translated versions of the Beck Anxiety Inventory, the Beck Depression Inventory, the Cognitive Failure Questionnaire, along with a Personal Information Form. Correlation analysis showed significant association among anxiety, depression, and everyday memory. Regression analysis revealed that anxiety and depression each made a significant independent contribution to the variance in everyday memory with a joint contribution of 32.7% variance. The findings have implications for health professionals, educators, and policy makers.

Keywords: Anxiety, Depression, Everyday Memory, Diploma, Nursing Student

Academic stress has been of significant interest for researchers as the process of education has been found very stressful (Manpreet & Maheshwari, 2015). University students experience situations that generate feelings such as frustration, fear, and anguish and cause academic, personal, and social stress during their academic activities (Kurupparachchi, Somerathna, Madurapperuma & Talagala, 2012). Thus, the environment that should be conducive to the development of professional knowledge sometimes contributes to the students' pathology (Gervasio et. al., 2012).

Nursing is one of the most stressful professions in the world (Najimi, Goudarzi & Sharifirad, 2012). Nursing students face stressful events in their study period that lead to negative consequences in their academic, professional and personal life (Damayanthi, 2014; Sharma & Kaur, 2011). A recent cross-sectional study carried out on 129 nursing students from a hospital in India found that 33.3% of the

respondents had depression from moderate to extreme level and 56.59% of the respondents suffered from anxiety on the same levels (Basu et al., 2016). Another recent investigation in Sri Lanka presented that more than half of their nursing students reported the presence of depression (51.1%) and anxiety (59.8%) (Rathnayake & Ekanayaka, 2016).

The relation between cognitive processes and depression has been of considerable interest in many investigations (Ellwart, Rinck & Becker, 2003). Depression alone seems to have negative effect on recalling information that are new (Kizilbash, Vanderploeg & Curtiss, 2002) and highly anxious participants have been found to have lower working-memory capacity than participants with low levels of anxiety (Darke, 1988).

Ample data suggest that depression and anxiety is high in nursing students and it is increasing with time (Basu et al., 2016). Moreover, strenuous events in their lives can

make them possibly prone to making mistakes (Zyga, 2013). But it appears that there has been very limited amount of research on everyday memory of nursing students and factors associated with it, especially in Bangladesh.

Bangladesh is a country of 43 government nursing institutes and 54 private nursing institutes with a number of affiliated nursing colleges. Here, under the Directorate of Nursing Services, two types of pre-service education in nursing are currently running. One is a Diploma in Nursing and another is B.Sc. in Nursing. In addition to pre-service education, there is also an opportunity to attain in-service or post basic education which aims to build the nurses as suitable candidates for nurse manager, nurse teacher, nurse administrator and nurse leader. More than 2000 students in pre-service programs and about 500 students in in-service programs are enrolled every year (DGNM, 2017).

Despite of the diversity of nursing programs and the vast number of people associated, there is not sufficient data regarding the mental health or performance of these students. Given this gap in knowledge, both in quality and quantity, the current study aims to explore the correlation between anxiety, depression and everyday memory among nursing students. Additionally, it aimed to investigate whether anxiety and depression have any independent contribution to the variance of everyday memory in nursing students.

Method

Participants

The sample consisted of 288 nursing students. Their ages ranged from 18 through 24 years with a mean age of 19.8 years ($SD = 0.96$). All the students were females and currently pursuing a Diploma in Nursing Science. The rationale behind selecting only female students was that majority of the nurses in Bangladesh are women (Begum, 1998; Zaman, 2009). They were purposively selected from two public nursing institutes near Dhaka, Bangladesh; one is Mitford Nursing Institute in Dhaka and the other is Nursing Institute in Munshiganj. The percentage of the students studying in

first, second and third year of the program were 37.2, 32.6 and 30.2 respectively. Prior to enrolling in a nursing program, 26.4% of the participants completed their HSC in science, 43.8% of them in humanities and 29.9% in business studies. At the time of data collection, 95% of the respondents resided in institution hostel and most of the students (94.8%) were unmarried. More than half of the students belonged to middle-class families with a mean family income of around 21,000 BDT. Parental (paternal and maternal) education was mostly below HSC. For example, 76.4% of the fathers and 97.6% of the mothers of the respondents did not continue their studies after HSC. About 93% of the respondents' mothers engaged in homemaking, and 35.4% of the fathers were in farming, 32.6% were in business and 20.8% were in service industries.

Measures

All participants in the research responded to a questionnaire package comprising of three self-report questionnaires along with a personal information form. The three measures included: (1) the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI); (2) the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI-II); and (3) the Cognitive Failure Questionnaire (CFQ). All of the questionnaires were translated into Bangla as it was the first language of all the participants. A brief description of each measure is given below.

Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI): The Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) (Beck, Epstein, Brown & Steer, 1988) used in the current research measures clinical anxiety. It is a self-report 21-item scale which includes symptoms that are common in anxiety. The respondents are asked to indicate how much they had been bothered by the items in the last four weeks. It has four response options ranging from 0 (Not at all) to 3 (Severely, I could barely stand it). So, the possible score ranges is 0 to 63; the higher the score means the higher is the anxiety. It showed high internal consistency with a Cronbach α of 0.92. The test-retest reliability of the scale was 0.75; had a moderate correlation ($r = .51$) with the revised version of Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale and a mild correlation ($r = .21$) with the

Hamilton Depression Rating Scale. The scale is also known to be capable of distinguishing between groups that are anxious and non-anxious. (Beck et al., 1988). In the present investigation, the scale was translated into Bangla language by Uddin and Shama (2017). The Bangla translated scale for the portion of the study showed high internal consistency reliability (Cronbach $\alpha = .86$).

Beck Depression Inventory (BDI- II): The Bangla version (Uddin & Ahmed, 2013) of the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) (Beck, Steer & Garbin, 1988) was used to assess the depression of participants. It is a self-administered scale with 21 items. The items included but not limited to mood, pessimism, libido, sleep disturbances and many more. Evidence suggests that BDI is capable to identify subcategories of depression and discriminate between depression and anxiety. A 25-year evaluation on the psychometric properties of the scale from 1961 to 1986 represent a high internal consistency of the scale for both psychiatric (mean Cronbach $\alpha = .86$) and nonpsychiatric patients (mean Cronbach $\alpha = .81$) (Beck, Steer & Garbin, 1988). The score of this 4-point scale ranges from 0 to 3, with the possible score ranges are 0 and 63, respectively. The higher score of the scale indicates higher level of depression and lower score indicates lower level of depression. With a few revisions, the most recent version of the scale is BDI-II, which is also a 21-item scale. The comparison between BDI-IA and BDI-II (1996) revealed that the later held higher internal consistency with a Cronbach α of .91 (Beck et al., 1996). The Bangla translated version used in the present study showed high internal consistency reliability (Cronbach $\alpha = .85$).

Cognitive Failure questionnaire (CFQ): The CFQ (Broadbent et al., 1982) was translated into Bangla (Uddin & Shama 2017) and administered to evaluate the condition of respondents' everyday memory. The CFQ is a 25-item scale which is used as self-report measure for failure in perception, deficit in memory, motor function (Broadbent et. al. 1982) and likelihood of committing a mistake in everyday activities

(Wallace, Kass & Stanny 2002). Respondents were asked to point the frequency that resembles the occurrence of their mistakes in conducting regular activities in the last six months. The latest version of the questionnaire provides response scale of 5-points ranging from 0 (never) to 4 (very often). The possible minimum and maximum score of the scale is 0 and 100 respectively where higher score suggests higher frequency of mistakes. The reexamination of CFQ by Wallace, Kass and Stanny (2002) showed that scale represents reliability with high internal consistency (Cronbach $\alpha = .76 - .86$). The translated Bangla version of the scale showed to have high internal consistency and reliability (Cronbach $\alpha = .90$).

Personal Information Form (PIF): The PIF was used to obtain demographic, social and economic information of the participants that included their age, background in HSC, current study year, residence, marital status, birth order, number of siblings including themselves, parents' education and occupation, socio-economic status and monthly income.

Procedure

The procedure of sample selection at both institutes was the same. For the collection of data, permission was sought from the appropriate authorities of the two institutes via written letter. Before giving the questionnaire package to any participant, the purpose of the study was briefed verbally. We assured the confidentiality of their responses by stating that any data provided by them would be used only for the purpose of the study and would not be revealed anywhere else. Along with written instruction, verbal instruction was delivered and any further confusion was clarified. Participants were asked to read every instruction carefully and requested to keep no item un-responded. Upon submitting, every questionnaire was screened carefully so that no question remained unanswered. On average, it took 30 minutes to complete the task. Members of the research team were present during data collection and assisted participants if anyone had any difficulty or confusion in reading, understanding and answering the questions.

To show gratitude for their participation, every respondent was thanked with a token gift.

Data Processing and Analysis

We used SPSS version 20 for processing the data. The scores on the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI), the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), the Cognitive Failure questionnaire (CFQ) and the information provided on the PIF were entered using SPSS. For the measurement of reliability of the three scales (BAI, BDI and CFQ), Cronbach α was computed. We computed descriptive statistics for HSC background, current study year, residence, marital status, birth order, number of siblings including themselves, parents' education and occupation, socio-economic status; mean score of age and family income were calculated as well. Total scores of BAI, BDI and CFQ for every participant were calculated and simple correlation was carried out with these scores to examine the relationships among major variables; namely anxiety, depression and everyday memory. Multiple regression analysis was carried out to examine the independent contributions of anxiety and depression on everyday memory.

Results

The first research objective, determining the correlation among anxiety, depression, and everyday memory among nursing students

was tested using simple correlations among the major variables in this study. The second research objective, determining whether anxiety and depression have any independent contribution to the variance of everyday memory in nursing students was examined using multiple regression. The dependent variable was cognitive failure. An F test has been performed to find if there were any differences among the major variables (i.e., anxiety, depression and cognitive failure) by study year which is presented in Table 1. Table 1 shows that there were no differences in the major variables by study year.

Table 2. Correlations among major variables in the present study (n = 288)

Variables	1	2	3
Anxiety	-	.58**	.51**
Depression		-	.50**
Cognitive failure			-

** Correlation is significant at the .01 level

We computed correlations among anxiety, depression, and cognitive failure on the entire sample since no differences among study year were observed. The results in Table 2 indicate that anxiety, depression, and cognitive failure are positively correlated with one another. Thus, the likelihood of committing mistakes would escalate

Table 1. Difference in major variables by study year

Variables		SS	df	MS	F	p
	Between Groups	300.89	2	150.44	1.57	.210
Anxiety	Within Groups	27333.054	285	95.90		
	Total	27633.94	287			
	Between Groups	264.32	2	132.16	1.44	.240
Depression	Within Groups	26238.29	285	92.06		
	Total	26502.61	287			
	Between Groups	1121.12	2	560.56	2.64	.073
Everyday Memory	Within Groups	60508.83	285	212.31		
	Total	61629.94	287			

with increasing anxiety ($r = .51$). Similarly, the more the depression in students, the more frequently they would make mistakes in their everyday lives ($r = .50$).

In order to find out the independent contribution of anxiety and depression to cognitive failure, we carried out multiple regression analysis (Table 3). The results revealed that anxiety and depression each made a significant and independent contribution to the difference in everyday memory. The value of standardized beta for anxiety ($\beta = .34$) reveals that the increase of 1 unit in anxiety increases 0.33 unit in cognitive failure. Similarly, the value of standardized beta for depression ($\beta = .31$) reveals that the increase of 1 unit in depression increases 0.31 unit in cognitive failure.

Table 3. Regression of Cognitive Failure on Anxiety and Depression (n = 288)

Predictors	B	β	t	P
(constant)	14.02		7.33	.000
Anxiety	.50	.34	5.67	.000
Depression	.47	.31	5.17	.000

* $R^2 = .327$ ($F = 69.34$, $p < .001$)

The model was significant ($F = 69.34$, $p < .001$) and explained additional 32.7% variance in everyday memory. Anxiety ($\beta = .337$, $p < .0001$) and depression ($\beta = .307$, $p < .001$) each significantly contributed to the variance in cognitive failure.

Discussion

This study examined whether anxiety and depression adversely affect everyday memory of nursing students. The sample consisted of 288 nursing students where all the students were females and currently pursuing a Diploma in Nursing Science. Their ages ranged from 18 through 24 years with a mean age of 19.8 years ($SD = 0.96$). They were purposively selected from two public nursing institutes near Dhaka, Bangladesh; one is Mitford Nursing Institute in Dhaka and the other is Nursing Institute in Munshiganj. In this study, cognitive failure has been used to assess the frequency of committing

mistakes in everyday life, thus functioning of everyday memory. Results showed that anxiety, depression and cognitive failure are positively correlated with each other. This result is consistent with findings of previous studies conducted in other countries. Previous studies show that anxiety is negatively correlated with the prospective component of memory (Arnold, Bayen & Böhm, 2015), and both encoding, and retrieval of information can be hampered by depression (Brand, Jolles & Wied, 1992). According to Kizilbash et al. (2002), the presence of depressive features can hamper instant recalling and addition of new information. According to this particular study, anxiety alone does not generate similar significant findings; but accompanied by depression, they can impose an adverse effect on memory. As anxiety is usually vigorously connected with depression (Nadeem, Ali, Maqbool & Zaidi, 2012), existence of either depression or anxiety can produce same consequences.

Result of regression analysis further revealed that both anxiety and depression made significant independent contribution to the variance of everyday memory. The regression analysis suggests that anxiety and depression together account for 32.7% variability in everyday memory of the participants. These findings are consistent with relevant studies which suggest that depression (Colby & Gotlib, 1988; Potter, Hartman & Ward, 2009) and anxiety can influence cognitive functioning (Potter et al., 2009).

According to previous literature review by Castaneda et al. (2008) on cognitive impairments in young adults with depression and anxiety it was found that the presence of cognitive impairments in people with anxiety and major depression is frequent. Symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression are highly prevalent among university students (Bayram & Bilgel, 2008) with a higher prevalence of depression among nursing students (Patel & Verma, 2017). The demands of a professional training can impose further challenges for nurses (Chernomas & Shapiro, 2013). Anxiety and depression along with affecting the cognitive

functioning (Colby & Gotlib, 1988; Castaneda et al., 2008; Potter et al., 2009) have a negative impact on their academic performance (Khurshid et al., 2015).

According to the American Nurses Association, nurses are involved in performing physical exams, administer medications, wound care, and numerous other personalized interventions. They are sometimes given the responsibility of administrative works (Zaman, 2009). Nursing education also requires critical thinking as their daily duties (Daly, 1998). Nurses are vital parts of operating room and preventing any kind of mistakes in an operating room has been reported as one of the key priorities (Alfredsdottir & Bjornsdotti, 2008). So, the outcome of any mistake while providing health care can lead to dreadful consequences.

It is important to acknowledge that the present study exhibits that depression and anxiety together can be held responsible for variance in cognitive failure thus functioning in everyday memory. Considering the consequences of any mistakes in clinical practice, a few studies have similar suggestions. Inam, Saqib, and Alam (2003) emphasized the availability of treatments and support services for students vulnerable to depression and anxiety.

The findings of the present study is not free of limitations. For example, the participants for the study were selected from only two nursing institutes. For this reason, it is difficult to generalize the findings for larger population. Also, due to lack of relevant studies on nursing in Bangladesh, we had to rely mostly on the findings from research carried out in the western countries, which is not entirely in concord with Bangladeshi contexts. Thus, the current research recommends for further investigation to address this issue.

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